

Using BCI Technique to Move the Head and Neck: Advanced Robotic Design to Improve Human-Machine Communication Experimentally and Theoretically

Muwafaq Abdullah Salih*
Al-Nahrain Univ., Dept. of Mechanical Engineering, Baghdad, Iraq
*Corresponding Author: mofak1981@gmail.com

Abstract

Patients with neurological diseases such as dropped head syndrome (DHS) and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) lack the ability of the neck muscles to keep their heads upright or control movement. The rehabilitation for this patient is the first step in treating head and neck movement so patients can eat, drink and socialize. Brain Computer Interface (BCI) technology also allows people to interact with devices by brain waves and execute commands without physical movement. The research including four parts. The first part of was design proposed head neck parallel configuration (3-RRS) manipulator structure includes the shoulders, backrest, motor holders, connecting links, head triangle, and head collar with their joints with six degrees of freedom, and three motors that move together to implement the six main of neck movements. The Finite Element Analysis (FEA) was used to test stress concentration while loading the head. All parts of the neck brace are designed in Solidwork program. The second part of the research is to apply and solve the equations for the chosen mechanism and find the values of the rotation angles for the six main neck movements theoretically, which were (rotation to right and left $\pm 70^\circ$, extension to up and flexion to down $\pm 55^\circ$, lateral bending to right and left $\pm 38^\circ$). The third part was manufacturing the parts by used PLA material of brace parts using 3D printing technology by (Crealty ender 3-pro) device and (Cura) program. The fourth part was to control the neck brace using the electroencephalography (EEG) signal, and the EEG data were acquired using (OPENBCI) device sensor of 16-channels. The acquired signals were pre-processed using a Savitzky–Golay filter, to extract features with an SVM method and a confusion matrix resolution of the EEG signals to classify them into categories applied to the six main movements of the neck. The EEG reading protocol was applied by taking six different trial experiments and applying (1875) samples/main movements, ultimately reaching (11,250) samples of any trial. The angles of neck movements were obtained experimentally using brain signals when the neck at rotating to right and left ($\pm 55^\circ$), extension to up and flexion to down ($\pm 42^\circ$), while lateral bending was to the right and left ($\pm 29^\circ$).

Keywords: Brain Computer Interface, Human-machine communication, Head and neck robotic, Savitzky–Golay filter, 3D printing technology

1. Introduction

Rehabilitation is the process of restoring a person's health or ability to lead a normal life through training and treatment. Recent studies also help clinical researchers to create new studies by building on the best evidence of future trials, implementation studies, and devices trial designs [1]. The most important part of rehabilitation is prescribing the appropriate assistive device with which the individual can perform regular duties or maintain proper posture with the help of these assistive devices [2]. The Brain Computer Interface (BCI) technology enables individuals to communicate with equipment by using only their brain waves as a form of communication. In order to issue commands and finish the interaction, there is no need for any additional gear or muscular activity [3]. Jingfang et al, in 2019 [4] in this paper, the 3-RXS mechanism, a parallel rigid and flexible mechanism, was developed as a neck brace for people with head drop symptoms (HDS). The neck brace e 3-RXS has a straightforward, lightweight design and excellent turning performance. Muhammad et al, in 2019 [5] This article introduces a dynamic neck rehabilitation robot with a new design that helps Dropped Head Syndrome patients attain their full natural range of head rotation while maintaining their safety. Cables are used to power the suggested robot. Three degrees of freedom (DOF) are offered by the proposed cable driven neck rehabilitation robot (CarNeck). But Pavan., Arockia., in 2019 [6] The concept of the parallel mechanism was used in this research to provide a unique and interesting wearable therapeutic device for the treatment of patients with head/neck posture problems. A parallel manipulator with three degrees

of freedom in a revolutionary prismatic-spherical configuration with three expandable bonds was introduced. Also, Biing et al, in 2021 [7] The full range of motion (ROM) of the neck was measured using a dynamic neck brace, which is presented in this article. Surface electromyography (EMG) has been used in conjunction with this slip-on brace. The head-neck anatomy serves as the brace's inspiration, and its design was influenced by the head-neck motion of ten healthy people.

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2. Method

2.1 Design process

After choosing the shape of the mechanism used (3-RRS) and designing all the required parts in the SolidWork program, an assembly of the parts was made and an experiment carried out in moving the brace was also in the virtual SolidWork program environment to give the six main movements required for the neck, which are (rotation to the right and left, extension to up and flexion to down, and then lateral bending to the right and left).

Then all the pieces were manufactured using 3D printing technology using a printer of the type (Creality Ender 3-pro) and (Cura) program, and using PLA biomaterial due to its specifications appropriate to the shape of the proposed mechanism within the required movements. The final assembly as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Final assembly of neck brace with operating accessories

2.2 Mathematical model

The main idea of the mechanism being used comes from reference [8]. 3-RRS means three revolute-link-revolute-link-spherical arms connected between the base (fixed-ground) and the end effector. Revolute joint allows rotation along a single axis, spherical joint allows rotation along all 3 axes, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Mechanism proposed and its constrained form where all the revolute axes pass through a single point C. S_b represents just the reference frame fixed to the fixed base (ground), S_p represents platform's moving frame, C is the point of intersection, and A_1 , A_2 , and A_3 represent spherical joint connections of three arms.

The alleviated the condition by constricting the sprained joints in each RRS arm at three distinct points. If we revisit the existing and reconstructed figures in Figure 3, points C1, C2, and C3 represent these three distinct points. In the right subfigure of Figure 3, they have presented here the kinematic parameters of one of the arms.

Figure 3. Mechanism proposed and kinematic analysis of the single arm [9]

Virtually, any work done by the end effector should be balanced by the work done by the torques as the system is conserved if everything is a rigid body. End effector does work on an external point P which is driven by the motors. The total work must be zero. Key point is, work is done through kinematics which requires previous analysis. Incremental motion steps are represented with the velocities.

Using the principle of virtual work, when the end-effector is balanced by the joint torques, the total work in the system should equal zero.

$$W_f + W_\tau = 0 \tag{1}$$

where W_f and W_τ are the virtual works achieved by a force applied on the end-effector and by torques applied on the proximal joints, respectively. W_f can be then expressed as:

$$W_f = \mathbf{f}_P \cdot \delta \mathbf{x}_P$$

where \mathbf{f}_P is the force applied at a reference point P on the end-effector and $\delta \mathbf{x}_P$ is a resultant infinitesimal displacement by \mathbf{f}_P .

Similarly, W_τ can be expressed as

$$W_\tau = \tau \cdot \delta\theta_1$$

where $\tau = [\tau_1 \ \tau_2 \ \tau_3]^T$ are the torques applied at the proximal joints and $\delta\theta_1$ are the angular displacements resulting from these torques. As δx_P and $\delta\theta_1$ are both arbitrarily small with a first order approximation, they can be replaced by the velocity of point P , v_P , and the rates of proximal joints, $\dot{\theta}_1$, respectively.

Substituting these two equations along into equation (1), one can obtain,

$$\begin{aligned} \because \dot{Q}_1 &= J_w w^2 \quad ; \quad \delta\dot{Q}_1 \cong \dot{Q}_1 \\ \because \tau \cdot \delta\theta_1 &= -f_p \cdot v_p \quad ; \quad \delta \times p \cong v_p = \dot{x}_p \\ \tau \cdot (J_w w^Q) &= -f_p \cdot v_p \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Because P is a fixed point on the end-effector, v_P can be expressed in terms of the linear and angular velocity of the end-effector,

$$v_P = v_Q + \omega^Q \times r_{QP}$$

Then, equation (2) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau \cdot (J_w w^Q) &= -f_p \cdot (v_Q + \omega^Q \times r_{QP}) \\ &= -f_p \cdot v_Q - \underbrace{f_p \cdot (\omega^Q \times r_{QP})}_{\text{identity}} \\ \tau \cdot (J_\omega \omega^Q)^2 &= (J_\omega^T \tau) \omega^Q = -f_p v_Q - (r_{QP} \times f_p) \times \omega^Q \\ \because (J_\omega^T \tau) \cdot \omega^Q &= -f_p \cdot v_Q - (r_{QP} \times f_p) \cdot \omega^Q \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Recalling the linear velocity of the end-effector is related to its angular velocity through matrix \mathbf{M} , there

$$(J_\omega^T \tau) \cdot \omega^Q = -(\mathbf{M}^T f_p + r_{QP} \times f_p) \cdot \omega^Q$$

where in equation (3):

$$v_Q = M w_Q$$

This equation holds true for all ω^Q . Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} J_\omega^T \tau &= -M^T f_p + r_{QP} \times f_p \\ \tau &= -(J_\omega^T)^{-1} (\mathbf{M}^T f_p + r_{QP} \times f_p) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

with equation (4), the torques required at the proximal joints to balance a specific force applied at a known point on the end-effector can be computed.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Theoretical results

The values of the maximum angles of the movements were calculated using the theoretical method shown the results in the Table 1 using this equation above.

Movement	Theoretical max. angle (degree)
Rotation to right	+ 70°
Rotation to left	- 70°
Up (Extension)	+ 55°
Down (Flexion)	- 55°
Lateral bending to right	+ 38°
Lateral bending to left	- 38°

3.2 Experimental results

After applying real-time readings of brain signals via the brain-computer interface to the neck brace experimentally, the maximum angles of the brace's movements were obtained using the gyroscope sensor (MPU6050) to specify the angles, and they were as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Maximum angles of experimentally for neck-brace

Movement	Maximum rotation angle experimentally
Rotation to right	+ 55°
Rotation to left	- 55°
Up (Extension)	+ 42°
Down (Flexion)	- 42°
Lateral Bending to right	+ 29°
Lateral Bending to left	- 29°

3.3. Comparison between angles of theoretical and experimental results

By comparing the theoretical results and practical results, the maximum angles of rotation for the main movements of the neck support were drawn through the Figure 4 for the movement of rotation to the right and left, and the Figure 5 for the movement up and down, while the Figure 6 is for the movement of lateral bending to the right and left. We notice that in all shapes, the values of the theoretical angles are greater than the experimental angles. In addition, notice that there is no oscillation in the theoretical method waveform is without, as in the experimental waveform.

Figure 4. Results of angles to rotation movement by theoretical and experimental

Figure 5. Results of angles to extension and flexion movement by theoretical and experimental.

Figure 6. Results of angles to lateral bending movement by theoretical and experimental.

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